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A Creative Folio

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Jubelita

O Taas, Baba ang mga tingin
Awra ko ba'y kapansin-pansin?
Sabay biglang tingin sa salamin
Pak! Ka-gwapa, Ang lakas ng dating.

Bakit unti-unting mukha'y nangingiwi
Tila tawa'y pinipigilan, Hoy! baka maihi,
Tiningnan uli ang sarili,
Pantay naman ang pula kong labi.

Araw't Gabi alindog ko'y makikita
Sarili'y minsan pinagmumukhang tanga
Para mga tao maging masaya
Bakit pagkatapos ng lahat ng patawa

Ika'y uli manghuhusga
Hoy, pagod na ako gaga
Pagod dahil lahat naman ginawa ko na!
Di niyo pa rin nakikita,
Na kami din ay tao ha!

Ayon may narinig akong sigaw
Malakas pero unti-unting napapagaw
Mukha'y namumula, tila ba'y bulalakaw.
Ay si Pudra na galit at gustong manghataw.